

AGROBIOHEAT: PROMOTING MODERN AGROBIOMASS HEATING SOLUTIONS IN RURAL EUROPE

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ABSTRACT: Different types of agrobiomass (agricultural residues, agroindustrial byproducts, fast growing energy crops and short rotation coppice) is an abundant, indigenous energy resource that can be effectively used for meeting the European decarbonisation targets. There are many potential models and technical pathways for utilizing agrobiomass in this sense; one of the most promising is its use as a heating fuel in European rural areas and in applications such as households and farms, municipal and commercial buildings, and agro-industries and greenhouses. Despite the existence of some agrobiomass heating markets in Europe, mostly based on agroindustrial biomass byproducts or straw, the full market potential of agrobiomass heating is not realized due several limiting factors. The present paper introduces AgroBioHeat (www.agrobioheat.eu), a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, that aims to develop into a comprehensive platform for the market uptake of agrobiomass heating solutions through the implementation of a variety of activities design to develop trust in the capacity of this technology to decarbonize the rural heating market, develop vision for its deployment and provide support to a number of initiatives that will be implemented by the project. The paper serves as an introduction to the current framework conditions for agrobiomass heating and to the overall strategy and approach followed by the AgroBioHeat project.

Keywords: agricultural residues, agroindustrial residues, energy crops, heat, rural development.

1 INTRODUCTION

Agrobiomass is a term used to describe a wide range of biogenic materials originating from agriculture. Among these, the most important for the bioenergy sector [1] are the following:

- **agricultural residues** from herbaceous crops (*e.g.* cereal straw, maize residues, rice straw, *etc.*) and permanent crops (orchard prunings and plantation removal wood)
- **agroindustrial by-products** (*e.g.* olive stones and olive cake, grape marc, sunflower husks, rice husk, *etc.*)
- **dedicated energy crops** of both herbaceous (*e.g.* miscanthus, switchgrass) and woody (*e.g.* Short Rotation Coppice such as poplar, willow) types.

If commercialized, agrobiomass can be found in various tradeable forms depending on its origin, harvesting system and final end-use: as whole bales (*e.g.* for straw), as shredded / hog-fuel / chips, as densified products (*e.g.* pellets, briquettes) or as granular materials (*e.g.* olive stones, rice husk).

The sustainable potential for agrobiomass in EU28 has been subject of public, policy and market interests, considering that Europe is proposing a low carbon economy based on growing rates of renewable energy, energy efficiency and an extended expansion of the bioeconomy. The available sustainable resources projected by 2030 refer to: biomass not utilised in other purposes (*e.g.* animal feeding), and not playing an environmental role (*e.g.* as organic amendment to preserve soil carbon pools).

A recent literature survey on the European biomass potential [2] indicates that the availability of agricultural by-products and residues that could be sustainably mobilized is in the range from 45 to 67 Mtoe on an annual basis, depending on the type of residues considered, impact of weather and soil protection measures. There is a much wider range for energy crops,

79 to 377 Mtoe, depending on various factors such as the land considered for production, crop diversity and species selection, intensity of agricultural management practices, *etc.* Taking into account that forest biomass resources (wood and related by-products and residues), the main biomass resource currently used for energy in Europe, are quantified as ranging from 5 to 174 Mtoe, it is clear that agrobiomass can play a crucial role in the further sustainable expansion of the renewable energy sector in Europe. The importance of agrobiomass in the future European energy system is especially high in assessments of NGOs [3], which adopt a quite strict outlook on the amounts of forest biomass that can be sustainably mobilized.

Agrobiomass is a currently underexploited as an energy resource. In fact, agrobiomass residues are mostly either disposed, left without significant contribution to soil, mulched and utilised as organic amendment or burnt on the field. This reality has been reported for multiple residues and countries [4]; on-field burning of the agricultural residues is responsible of 8 % (35 kt/yr) of PM10 emissions, 11 % (22.4 kt/yr) of PM2.5 emissions and 3 % of NMVOC (Non-methane volatile organic compounds) released by the agriculture in Europe.

Denmark is a notable exception to the under-utilization of agrobiomass; in 2016, energy production from straw amounted to 19.6 PJ or 12.6 % of the total renewable energy production [5].

2 THE EUROPEAN HEATING SECTOR

2.1 The overall perspective

While the share of RES in the electricity, heating & cooling and transport sectors in the EU have increased since 2009 (and earlier), it was the RES electricity sector that has received the “lion’s share” of the attention through the introduction of specific policy instruments both on the European level, as well as on the national level. However, the heating & cooling sector corresponds

to 50 % of final energy consumption, while more than 80 % of the sector consumption is based on non-renewable energy sources [6]. It is interesting to note that biomass is by far the largest renewable energy sector for the heating & cooling sector, with an 87 % share compared to 10 % for heat pumps, 2 % for solar thermal and 1 % for geothermal energy [7]. Reaching the EU's energy and climate goals (e.g. at least 27 % share of renewable energy consumption till 2030), means that significant efforts still need to be spent on the penetrating RES solutions to the heat market. It is also clear that bioenergy is the most mature technology in the heating sector and, considering the large share of fossil fuel usage, still has room for further deployment.

2.2 Heating markets in the European rural areas

In the five-year period from 2010-2015, there has been a gradual increase of the rural population in the EU-28, which reached 28 % of the total population in 2015 [8]. Comprehensive EU-level statistics on the energy or heat consumption of the rural sector are lacking. An earlier study [9] highlights the differences between rural areas of several member states; as a general rule, rural areas tend to use more biomass than urban areas. However, since the absence of natural gas infrastructure is common in such areas, rural consumers tend to consume more fossil fuels with high carbon intensity for heating (e.g. oil and in some cases coal). Hence, despite the increased use of biomass, this results in higher GHG emissions per capita compared to urban or semi-urban areas. Similar findings are also reported in other studies [10] and some national statistical reports highlight the higher energy consumption of rural households compared to urban ones [11].

The biomass market in European rural areas is dominated by wood products. In southern European countries, agro-industrial by-products such as olive stones and nut shells have a market share comparable to those of wood pellets [12]; such biomass fractions are readily available in some rural areas and are used – apart from domestic fuels – as fuels for industrial purposes. Detailed statistics on agrobiomass use in Europe are lacking. Some indications can be gained from the fact that from the whole of the European pellet market, only 10 % corresponds to the production of non-woody pellets, which are usually consumed by industrial (power or CHP) plants [13].

3 BENEFITS AND BARRIERS FOR AGROBIOMASS HEATING

3.1 Benefits of agrobiomass heating

Considering the overall boundary conditions, the use of agrobiomass as a fuel for heating applications appears to have several advantages. It is an indigenous fuel source, available in large quantities in rural areas, which often have a high heat demand. Deployment of other solutions, for example natural gas heating, in those locations might require larger infrastructure investments than the expected benefits, and still without providing a renewable energy solution. Agrobiomass can be cost effective compared to fossil fuels, leading to reductions of the annual fuel costs for end-users.

An extended use of agrobiomass improves the environment in various ways. Being a carbon neutral energy source, it does not contribute to greenhouse gas

emissions. If the use of agrobiomass results in the reduction of open-field burning of residues, then uncontrolled emissions are also reduced.

Finally, the use of agrobiomass for heating is fully in line with concepts related to rural development, circular economy and has positive impact on social aspects; for example, it can lead to creation of new jobs in rural areas related to agrobiomass logistics and operation of agrobiomass heating facilities.

3.2 Market uptake barriers

Increasing the share of agrobiomass in the energy mixture – and in particular in the heat sector – is considered as a challenging task. In most areas, potential adopters of agrobiomass heating solutions face the following issues when considering starting a new application:

- They may only be aware of limited technological options for agrobiomass combustion; they do not have sufficient evidence as to the capacity of these options meet current or future emission standards. Moreover, they might perceive agrobiomass as a “difficult” fuel, which can cause operating and emissions problems.
- They face a chicken-and-egg problem for fuel sourcing: setting up a new supply chain requires efforts which may not pay off if the end demand is not yet in place.
- Even if they can bypass all these problems, they might consider that the additional investment costs associated with agrobiomass are simply “not worth it”.

All these issues together with a lack of support and a clear vision of how to proceed and what the benefits are, make that most potential adopters abandon the agrobiomass option and choose the “path of least resistance”: heating solutions for which there is already a developed market, e.g. fossil fuels or wood biomass. As mentioned earlier, agro-industrial by-products often bypass the fuel sourcing issue, since they are already readily available at the agro-industries where they are produced, without the need to employ additional harvesting and logistics operations; hence a local market for such resources often exists. For other cases, (e.g. agricultural residues) however, only a few visionaries break out of this vicious circle and start their own agrobiomass heating cases. These “lighthouse examples” may be very successful but are usually of a very local character; as a result, they receive little publicity out of specialized circles and cannot fulfil their potential to serve as imitation examples for others.

3.3 Technical issues and solutions for agrobiomass combustion

Out of the barriers mentioned above, it is worth to take a closer look at the “technical” ones. Most types of agrobiomass indeed exhibit higher contents of N, S, Cl and ash forming elements, as well as lower ash melting temperatures, than conventional wood fuels. These characteristics often lead to problems with reduced plant efficiency and availability due to slagging and increased emissions, especially of particulate matter (PM).

However, during recent years some of the leading European biomass boiler manufacturers have developed specific combustion systems, which are also suitable for

agrobiomass. Therefore, nowadays already some reliable technologies are available, also in the small and medium capacity range. Moreover, driven by the gradually reducing dust emission limits in Germany according to the Small and Medium Size Firing Installations Ordinance (1. BImSchV), a development of dust precipitator technologies (mainly electrostatic precipitators – ESP) for small-scale wood boilers has taken place [14]. These technologies have already achieved a high level of maturity and, in the case of agrobiomass utilisation, they can represent an opportunity for low-PM emission operation at acceptable costs.

The technologies mentioned above are typically based on grate combustion systems. Further R&D efforts are also undertaken aiming to produce new concepts for combustion systems with increased fuel flexibility characteristics. For instance, a small-scale updraft gasifier directly coupled with a gas burner and a boiler has been developed and introduced by the Austrian company Windhager which allows for wood pellet and wood chip combustion at almost zero CO and OGC emissions and at PM emissions of below 2 mg/MJ (related to the fuel NCV) without the application of any filter. Within the Horizon 2020 project FlexiFuel-CHX (<http://www.flexifuelchx.eu>) this concept is further developed towards higher fuel flexibility. Published results show the high potential of this technology for low-PM emission operation (<5 mg/MJ) without any need for filters also when utilising agrobiomass such as miscanthus pellets [15]. Comparable fuel-flexible low-emission technologies are also under development for the medium capacity range (>500 kW).

4 THE AGROBIOHEAT APPROACH

AgroBioHeat (www.agrobioheat.eu) is a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the topic LC-SC3-RES-28-2018-2019-2020 – Market Uptake support (for renewable energy technologies).

The main objective of **AgroBioHeat** project is to produce a mass deployment of improved and market ready heating solutions running on agrobiomass in Europe. Through its activities, **AgroBioHeat** aims to raise confidence on agrobiomass, empower local stakeholders to unblock the market and influence the development of the European and national framework in a way that is favourable to agrobiomass heating solutions market uptake.

From a technical point of view, **AgroBioHeat** targets mainly small-medium systems (from around 50 kW to 1 MW) for heat generation (in agro-industries, farms, rural heat networks, public and commercial buildings, *etc.*) where there is currently a gap on the use of agrobiomass. In that line, **AgroBioHeat** aims also to contribute to the increase of the distributed energy production, improving the carbon footprint by optimising the matching between the energy resource production and energy consumption sites.

4.1 Strategy for market uptake: the project approach

The AgroBioHeat strategy is to implement a series of activities aligned in three layers, and having the overall aim of an increased penetration of agrobiomass heating, especially in the rural areas. The keywords for those layers are **trust**, **vision** and **support**. These components

are arranged on a pyramid scheme (Figure 1); apart from its logical founding (e.g. vision builds on trust), it is an indication of the expected outreach of each type of activity. Project outputs that generate “trust” will be accessible to a very wide audience and widely disseminated. On the other hand, specific support activities can be provided to a reduced number of beneficiaries in the framework of an ongoing project.

Figure 1: The AgroBioHeat pyramid of trust, vision and support

Some examples of **AgroBioHeat** activities related to the development of **trust** in agrobiomass heating solution are the following:

- Development of an Agrobiomass Heating Observatory, a map-based directory for displaying various relevant actors (e.g. equipment manufacturers, fuel providers, adopters, *etc.*).
- Detailed study of existing success cases and reporting / visualization of them so that they can serve as examples for imitation.
- Organization of site-visits to success cases.
- Targeted dissemination actions, e.g. presentations in conferences, events, *etc.*
- Performance testing of modern agrobiomass heating devices in both lab-scale as well as in operating facilities. The results will be used to prove the modern agrobiomass heating solutions are efficient and capable of meeting high environmental standards.

In order to generate **vision** for the role of agrobiomass heating in the future energy system, **AgroBioHeat** will implement – among others – the following activities:

- Development of policy roadmaps and recommendations for the multiplication countries (see below) as well as on an EU level. These documents will be promoted through a series of policy workshops and advocacy actions.
- Increased sector visibility in fairs & expos through the setting up of stands, display of promotion material, facilitating matchmaking between potential adopters and equipment providers, *etc.*
- Implementation of a number of social surveys, as well as local / regional workshops and community hearings, that aim to align the general public with the final goal of the project.

Finally, when it comes to providing specific **support** for the issues related to market uptake of agrobiomass heating solutions, the following activities will be implemented:

- A specific accompaniment / support to new initiatives aiming to deploy agrobiomass heating will be offered by the project partners. The initiatives could involve a number of different actors. For example, it could be a municipal council working together with the local agricultural cooperative; the former would install agrobiomass heating boilers in municipal buildings, while the latter would provide the fuel needed for the operation. The accompaniment could take different types depending on the needs of the actors involved, *e.g.* technical assistance for setting up a supply chain, consultancies on appropriate choice of heating systems, setting up a funding campaign, *etc.*
- Results of the combustion tests performed by the project will be sent to policy actors working on the revision of the Ecodesign Regulation; the aim is to include specific limits for agrobiomass heating that can work towards the sustainable development of the market.
- A series of trainings will be offered to installers of biomass heating systems, aiming to familiarize them with specific issues related to the installation, operation and maintenance of agrobiomass heating solutions.

4.2 Target & key actors

The main target actors of AgroBioHeat are the main potential adopters of agrobiomass heating solutions in a rural context: ESCOs & installers, renewable energy cooperatives, the public sector, farms and agro-industries. They are the market actors that are the most well positioned to create a significant and measurable change in the local heating market by embracing agrobiomass as a fuel source.

ESCOs and installers have the capacity to deploy agrobiomass heating solution to a large market, provided they are confident in the performance of this technology option. With a specialised team (*e.g.* fuel sourcing department, maintenance personnel), they might be well suited to deal with the peculiarities of agrobiomass heating, while leaving the benefits of its use (*e.g.* lower heating bills) to their final customers.

The public sector is often by itself a significant heat consumer on a local level (*e.g.* at public buildings such as schools, swimming pools, *etc.*). By adopting agrobiomass heating, the public sector can immediately create a sizeable market demand. It can also serve as a powerful local example for imitation, while simultaneously being better suited to deal with initial risk compared to private entrepreneurs.

Farms and agro-industries can also be significant heat consumers on a local rural level. In the case of agroindustries, apart from being able to generate a sizable demand for agrobiomass on their own, they can have a key role to play as intermediate centers for agrobiomass upgrading and distribution, as per the Integrated Biomass Logistics Centre (IBLC) concept.

Renewable energy cooperatives (REScoops) &

Energy Communities are business models undergoing expansion in Europe; citizens and other local actors jointly own and participate in renewable energy or energy efficiency projects. Most REScoops operate on a local or regional basis and are thus excellently positioned to mobilize a local energy resource like agrobiomass, which might be provided by their own members. In addition, REScoops members can immediately witness the local benefits (not only tangible ones) of an agrobiomass heating concept.

In addition to the target actors, three sets of key actors are also critical for AgroBioHeat: policy makers, manufacturers and the local community.

Policy makers set the overall legal framework into which agrobiomass heating solutions operate; in addition, they have the power to set up appropriate financial support measures which can facilitate the market penetration of the technology. Policy makers at all levels of government (local, regional, national and EU) are targeted by the project activities through specific advocacy actions. On the European level in particular, a key project activity is associated with the review of the Ecodesign regulation with the potential inclusion of “non-woody” biomass boilers in its scope and the recommendation for emissions limits in biomass facilities from 500 kW to 1 MW.

Manufacturers of combustion equipment and flue gas cleaning systems provide the technological solutions for agrobiomass heating. Several European manufacturers have made advances in combustion technology that can lead to very low emissions for agrobiomass combustion. The achievements of these systems have to be thoroughly documented so that they can be a basis for any regulatory revisions and the opportunities should be spread to the potential adopters.

The local community can have an influence on the policy makers (especially on the local / regional level) and the potential adopters. The acceptance of the local community is critical to the success of agrobiomass heating for several reasons. For example, it is local people (*e.g.* farmers) that provide the agrobiomass in the first place. Moreover, if the local community is not convinced of the environmental impact of a technology option, then serious local opposition may emerge. For this reason, AgroBioHeat intends to understand and shape the perception of the local community members.

4.3 Geographical scope and consortium

Most of the project activities aiming to promote agrobiomass heating will be implemented in six multiplication countries. Project partners representing biomass & bioenergy, renewable energy or agricultural associations & clusters in these countries will be instrumental for the success of these activities:

- **Spain:** Spanish Biomass Association – AVEBIOM
- **Croatia:** Green Energy Cooperative – ZEZ (Croatia)
- **Romania:** Green Energy Innovative Biomass Cluster
- **Greece:** Institute for Agricultural and Co-operative Economy – INASO-PASEGES
- **France:** Association of Local Initiatives in the field of Energy and Environment
- **Ukraine:** Bioenergy Association of Ukraine – UABIO

Technical expertise and support will be provided by three partners with well-known backgrounds in the field of biomass & bioenergy: CERTH (Greece), Fundacion CIRCE (Spain) and BIOS BIOENERGIESYSTEME (Austria). Policy and advocacy actions will be led by Bioenergy Europe (Belgium), while social expertise is provided by White Research (Belgium). Agro Business Park (Denmark) leads empowerment and multiplication activities and provides valuable expertise from an EU country that is known globally as a forerunner in the energetic utilization of straw. Finally, Agronergy, a company that is already operating biomass heating facilities in France, will investigate agrobiomass solutions in its existing or new installations.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Agrobiomass is a large, underexploited and indigenous resource, which can support the achievement of the European Energy and Climate targets, while promoting rural development and circular economy. The **AgroBioHeat** project aims to produce a mass deployment of improved and market ready agrobiomass heating solutions in Europe. AgroBioHeat actions will take place mostly in 6 European countries (Croatia, France, Greece, Romania, Spain, Ukraine). The implementation strategy of the project includes a series of actions aiming to foster trust, develop vision and provide support for the deployment of agrobiomass heating in Europe.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Bioenergy Europe, Factsheet “Biomass for Energy: Agricultural Biomass & Energy Crops”, (2018). https://bioenergyeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Factsheet_ABEC_Final.pdf
- [2] A.P.C. Faaij, Securing sustainable resource availability of biomass for energy applications in Europe; review of recent literature, (2018). <https://bioenergyeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Bioenergy-Europe-EU-Biomass-Resources-Andr%C3%A9-Faaij-Final.pdf>
- [3] Birdlife & Transport & Environment, How much sustainable biomass does Europe have in 2030? A briefing, (2016). www.transportenvironment.org
- [4] O. Oenema, G. Velthof, Z. Klimont, W. Winiwarer, Emissions from agriculture and their control potentials, (2012), TSAP Report. Contract with DG-ENV (ENV.C.3/SER/2011/0009) of DG-Environment of the European Commission. http://ec.europa.eu/environment/air/pdf/TSAP-AGRI-20121129_v21.pdf
- [5] Danish Energy Agency, Energy Statistics 2016, (2018). http://ens.dk/sites/ens.dk/files/Statistik/energy_statistics_2016.pdf
- [6] Eurostat. Energy for heating / cooling from renewable sources, (2019). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20190304-1>
- [7] Bioenergy Europe, Statistical Report, (2018). <https://bioenergyeurope.org/statistical-report-2018/>
- [8] Eurostat, Statistics on rural areas in the EU h, (2017). [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Statistics_on_rural_areas_in_the_EU)

- [explained/index.php/Statistics_on_rural_areas_in_the_EU](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Statistics_on_rural_areas_in_the_EU)
- [9] Ecofys, Rural energy in the EU. Country studies for France, Germany, Italy, Poland and the UK, (2011). <http://www.shvenergy.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/full-report.pdf>
- [10] K. Meirmans, Household direct energy consumption and CO2 emissions in European countries, (2013). Default journal. https://www.rug.nl/research/portal/files/14422209/EE_S-2013-171T_KoenMeirmans.pdf
- [11] Hellenic Statistical Authority, Press Release: Survey on Energy Consumption in Households 2011-2012, (2013) <http://www.statistics.gr/documents/20181/985219/Energy+consumption+in+households/>
- [12] Biomasud Plus, Residential heating biofuels market state of the art, (2017). http://biomasudplus.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/D2.1-Market_report_Consolidated-6.pdf
- [13] AEBIOM, Annual Statistical Report: European Bioenergy Outlook, (2017). <http://www.aebiom.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/FINAL-AEBIOM-2017-STATISTICAL-REPORT.pdf>
- [14] A. Bologa, M. Ecker, H.P. Rheinheimer, H.R. Paur, Development and Demonstration of an Electrostatic Precipitator, which is Optimally Adapted to a Biomass Boiler, (2016). Proceedings of the 24th European Biomass Conference and Exhibition, pag. 434 – 440. DOI: 10.5071/24thEUBCE2016-2AO.5.4
- [15] I. Obernberger, T. Brunner, C. Mandl, M. Kerschbaum, T. Svetlik, Strategies and technologies towards zero emission biomass combustion by primary measures, (2017). Energy Procedia 120, pag. 681–688. DOI: 10.1016/j.egypro.2017.07.184

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